

Amidomethylation with Salicylamide¹: Part III.

Guru Bachan Singh, B. B. Dixit and V. K. Vijjan

A few amidomethylations with *N*-hydroxymethyl salicylamide and compounds containing a hydrogen of pronounced reactivity have been carried out using Einhorn/Tscherniac procedure.

Amidomethylation^{2,3} was carried out by condensing equimolecular quantities (0.01-0.02 *M*) of *N*-hydroxymethyl salicylamide and compounds containing reactive hydrogen in acid medium.

N-Hydroxymethyl salicylamide⁴ was prepared by warming salicylamide (13.7 g, 0.1M) with 38% solution of formaldehyde (25 ml *ca.* 0.12 *M*) and anhydrous potassium

FIG. 1

FIG. 2

1. Paper presented at the XVIII Indian Pharmaceutical Congress, held on the 28th December, 1963 at Bombay.
2. H. Hellmann, *Angew. Chem.*, 1957, **69**, 463.
3. Zaig and Martin, *Organic Reactions*, 1965, **14**, 52.
4. A. Einhorn *et al.*, *Ann. Chem. Liebigs.*, 1905, **343**, 255.

carbonate (ca. 2 g in 20 ml water). The reaction mixture was warmed on a water bath till a clear solution was obtained. The mixture was then cooled at 0°. Within two or three hours the crystals of N-hydroxymethyl salicylamide appeared. Yield: 12 g (ca. 70%), m.p. 126-27° (Lit. 126-28°).

Amidomethylation reactions were carried out either by Einhorn⁵ or Tscherniac⁶ procedure.

Einhorn Procedure: The compound containing reactive hydrogen atom (0.1 M) was dissolved in the minimum quantity of ethanol (10-12 ml); and to this solution was added N-hydroxymethyl salicylamide (0.1 M) under shaking and warming, if necessary, to affect solution. After the addition of conc. HCl (1-2 ml), the reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for 2-3 hr. In the case of β -naphthanol and thymol, the products separated simply on cooling, while in other cases it appeared on dilution with cold water. Incidentally thymol required as much as 16 ml of conc. HCl as a condensing agent. For catechol, better yield was obtained by passing dry HCl gas in the reaction mixture in ethanol till saturation. Condensation of N-hydroxymethyl salicylamide with salicylamide, succinimide, sulphonamide, thymol, β -naphthol, hexylresorcinol and catechol were carried out successfully by this method.

Tscherniac Procedure: The amidomethylation was carried out by dissolving the reactive hydrogen compound in conc. H₂SO₄ (15-20 ml) and adding to it gradually under cooling N-methylol of salicylamide and leaving the reaction mixture at room temperature for two days. The reaction mixture was then poured on crushed ice. The amidomethylation product precipitated and was washed with water in order to remove the sulphonated products. It was recrystallised from the appropriate solvent—ethanol, benzene, xylene, ethyl acetate etc. Condensation of the N-hydroxymethyl salicylamide with phthalimide, benzamide, antipyrin, *p*-cresol, nicotinamide, *p*-nitrophenol and benzoic acid were successfully carried out by this method.

TABLE I

S.N.	Name of the compound —R	Molecular formula	Mol. wt.	Yield%	M.P.+ °C	%Nitrogen°	
						Found	Reqd
1.	N-Hydroxymethyl salicylamide*	C ₈ H ₉ O ₃ N	167.0	70	126-27	—	—
2.	Methylene-bis-salicylamide*	C ₁₅ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂	286.0	50	194-95	9.45	9.77
3.	1-Salicylamidomethyl pyrrolidinē 2:4 dione	C ₁₂ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂	248.0	40	170-72	10.83	11.28
4.	N-Salicylamidomethyl phthalimide	C ₁₆ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂	296.0	80	198-200	9.05	9.45
5.	Salicylamidomethyl benzamide*	C ₁₇ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂	294.0	40	152	9.25	9.52
6.	Salicylamidomethyl sulfonamide	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N ₃ S	321.0	50	260 (Dec.)	12.65	13.08

5. A. Einhorn *et al.*, *ibid.* 1905, **343**, 207.

6. J. Tscherniac, German patent, 134979 and 134980 (1902)

7. P. Friedländer, *Fortschritte der Teerfarben Fabrikation und verwandter Industriezweige*, 1902, **6**, 143-35. Springer Verlag.

TABLE I (Contd.)

S. N.	Name of the compound —R	Molecular formula	Mol. wt.	Yield	M.P.+ °C%	Nitrogen°	
						Found	Reqd.
7.	4-Salicylamidomethyl-1-phenyl 3:5 dimethyl 5-pyrazolone	C ₁₉ H ₁₉ O ₃ N ₃	337.0	40	110-12	11.95	12.43
8.	<i>o</i> -Salicylamidomethyl thymol (3 hydroxy- 4-isopropyl toluene)*	C ₁₈ H ₂₁ O ₃ N	299.0	50	169-71	4.25	4.68
9.	α -Salicylamidomethyl β -naphthol	C ₁₈ H ₁₅ O ₃ N	293.0	85	120-22	4.30	4.77
10.	Salicylamidomethyl <i>p</i> -cresol	C ₁₅ H ₁₅ O ₃ N	257.0	30	118-20	4.99	5.44
11.	N-Salicylamidomethyl saccharin (<i>o</i> -benzoic sulphimide)	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₅ N ₂ S	332.0	55	216-18 (Dec.)	7.85	8.43
12.	Salicylamidomethyl hexyl resorcinol	C ₂₀ H ₂₅ O ₄ N	343.0	45	270 (Dec)	3.90	4.08
13.	Salicylamidomethyl catechol*	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	259.0	40	200-202	5.10	5.40
14.	Salicylamidomethyl nicotinamide	C ₁₄ H ₁₃ O ₃ N ₃	271.0	30	170-72	15.25	15.49
15.	Salicylamidomethyl <i>p</i> -nitrophenol	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₄ N ₂	270.0	35	215-17	9.85	10.29
16.	<i>m</i> -Salicylamidomethyl benzoic acid	C ₁₅ H ₁₃ O ₄ N	271.0	54	98-100	4.76	5.16

*Already reported by Einhorn *et. al.*, *Ann.*, **343**, 255 (1905)

†All m.p.s. are uncorrected °Nitrogen by Kzeldahl.

It is apparent from the table I that the amidomethylation proceeds with greater facility and ease, the greater the nucleophilic potential of the reactive hydrogen component. It may be noted that even aromatic compounds, which possess nucleophilic potential inadequate for Mannich Condensation, such as benzoic acid, are susceptible to amidomethylation.

THE MANNICH RESEARCH SCHOOL,
PHARMACEUTICAL CHEMISTRY DIVISION,
COLLEGE OF TECHNOLOGY,
BANARAS HINDU UNIVERSITY,
VARANASI-5.

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